

2014

***Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education
Research Journal (AMIERJ)***

***(Bi-Monthly)
Peer-Reviewed Journal
Impact factor: 0.948***

VOL - III Issues: V

***Chief-Editor:
Ubale Amol Baban***

30/11/2014

**A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF INDIA & BHUTAN IN CONTEXT OF
ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE AND SELF-PERCEIVED ROLE
EFFICACY**

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Abstract:

The study investigated the comparative study of India and Bhutan in context of Organizational Climate and Self-perceived Efficacy among Indian and Bhutanese teachers by surveying 1015 teachers (445 from India and 579 from Bhutan). In order to appreciate the overall of effect of organizational climate upon self-perceived efficacy among Indian and Bhutanese teachers the average score of all the 69 items of the inventory by Kumar and Mutha for measuring self efficacy and Organizational Climate Inventory (OCI) developed by Chattopadhyay and Aggarwal (1976) for measuring Organizational Climate has been considered. Results revealed that there is relative contribution of organizational climate on self-perceived efficacy of teachers for India, Bhutan and jointly for both the countries. Study also indicates that the teachers belonging to the functional work climate of Bhutan not only are high in perceiving their self-perceived efficacy but are consistent in their approach. The scores between dysfunctional work climate and functional work differ significantly among both the countries. By applying Manova Technique, all results are insignificant regarding gender, urban/rural, schools /colleges, age, experience like variables.

Keywords: Organizational Climate, Self-perceived efficacy, Comparative Education, India, Bhutan.

Back-Drop:

Being a social entity in any country, Every Educational institutions has its own organizational climate in which teachers are giving best contribution of their worth. Organizational climate of all type of educational institutions across the world face a host of new and ongoing concerns related with Self Efficacy of teachers. Teacher self-efficacy is linked to persistence and effort during instruction (Gibson & Dembo (1984). Self-efficacy is a motivational construct based on self-perception of competence and researches revealed the fact that a teacher's self-perceived level of competence may not be having any effect in given organizational climate.

The self-efficacy is related with the individual perception of environment and personal talents.(Belkis&Mithat:2014).Organizational climate refers to common practices, shared beliefs, and value systems that an organization follows (Chen and Huwang, 2007; Janz et al, 1997). For individual members of an organization, climate can be explained as a set of expectations and attributes that describe the overall pattern of organizational activities (Jaw and Liu: 2003). Efficacy beliefs of preservice teachers have been linked to attitudes towards children and control (Woolfolk & Hoy :1990).Teachers' efficacy is related with how much a teacher believes he can effectively complete the tasks that his or her profession of teaching requires, so that students get hold of the skills required for learning.No doubt the administrative effectiveness and personality of the educational administrators is also important as these factors shape the climate of the educational Institution.Now world is shrinking in small village and through cross-cultural comparison we are able to compare the different psychological attributes of educational issues in different countries. Some Researcher reported that Effect of Organizational climate is not always having amenable impact upon Self perceived efficacy of teachers' .Jaafari, Karami and Soleimani (2012) revealed in their findings that there is a meaningful correlation between Organizational Learning and Self Efficacy. On the other hand, the correlation between Organizational Climate and Self Efficacy indicates that there is no relationship between these

two variables. Wayne Jennifer L. Edwards, Kathy E. Green, Cherie A. Lyons, (2002) in their study examined the personal empowerment and efficacy of teachers, and relates these constructs to environmental characteristics in order to provide information for principals to assist teachers in personal growth. Shacklock, Manning & Hort (2013) revealed that a small number of studies have incorporated both Organisational Climate and Self Efficacy. The very objective of the paper is to compare the significant effect of Organizational Climate on Self perceived Efficacy of Indian and Bhutan as a matter of international comparisons under Comparative Education.

Rational of the statement:

Because being neighboring countries, India and Bhutan contribute to each other uniquely warm and special relations founded on mutual trust and understanding. Regular high-level exchange of visits, close consultations and mutually beneficial cooperation underpin relations with Bhutan, Both countries share a common perception of their strategic interests and cooperate closely on security issues and border management (Voiceofindia.com, 2013). After visualize this particular relationship with each other, an idea has been conceptualized to compare both countries in terms of Organizational Climate and Self Perceived Efficacy with reference to Educational Institutions. These types of important educational questions can best be examined from an International and Comparative perspective. There are two main approaches to analyzing variation in educational performance across countries: best practice benchmarking and regression analysis. Present research paper has solved the research question by using regression analysis. It is the need of the hour that we should explore cross national comparisons in context of teaching learning situation. Marsh & Hau(2004) found international comparisons provide researchers with new knowledge about the universality and general ability of important psychological constructs, and allow future investigations to include the newly validated constructs in a more diverse range of settings. Marsh & Hau(2004) again stated that Cross-national comparisons are useful theory-builders as they provide researchers with “a valuable heuristic basis to test the external validity and generalizability of their measures, theories, and models, Triandis (1996)

explored that Because these comparisons offer a way of exploring the universality of psychological constructs and measures. Punia & Kaushik (2012) are of the view that teachers are same in their perception and their philosophies are also same across the boundaries. In Indian literature little efforts have been made concerning comparative studies of teaching efficacy with international context. Y.N. Sridhar and Hamid Reza Badiei (2008) to determine the differences in teacher efficacy level between Indian and Iranian higher primary schoolteachers. Overall participant teacher efficacy scores were almost high. Statistically no significant difference in general teaching efficacy scores were found between two countries.

Statement of the Problem

At the outset it is essential to list the statement of the problem that the study wishes to address. Accordingly the statement of the problem for the present study is 'A Comparative study of India & Bhutan in context of Organizational Climate and Self-perceived Role Efficacy

Conceptual Framework:

Organizational Climate: Broadly speaking, Organizational climate refers to the shared perceptions of employees regarding organizational functioning and practices (Yahyagil: 2006). It is about the internal environment which is experienced by the members. It influences the behaviour of the people in the organization. It is an abstract and intangible concept, remain stable over a period of time and reflects the employee perception about his organization, i.e., it reflects a person's perception of the organization to which he belongs and it serves as a major force influencing their behaviour.

Self-perceived efficacy: It is a term used in corresponding to a person's belief in their own competence. It has been defined as the belief that one is capable of performing in a certain manner to attain certain goals. One such factor that might have an impact on how teachers perform in the classroom is Teacher Efficacy. Teacher Efficacy has been positively associated with academic achievement in students. Self-perceived Efficacy refers to perception of self

competence, a sense of autonomy and a belief in ones academic capabilities. It is perceived ability to succeed at a specific task and an internal component of motivation. In its general sense, the extent to which an individual considers his capabilities sufficient to fulfill a task is stated as his Self-Efficacy perception. This belief is formed in consequence of a detailed analysis and judgment made by the individual for his capabilities. The individual analysis his abilities, skills, personal traits, knowledge and experience, motivation-that is, his capabilities to respond to the requirement of the situation he is in. If he believes that the capabilities are sufficient for the task, activity or the situation, he takes action.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the present study will be as under:

1. To know the relative contribution of overall Organizational Climate the Self-Perceived Efficacy of teachers' across India and Bhutan and jointly for both the countries
2. To know the interactive effect of Organizational Climate, the country and the type of institution (working in schools or colleges) on the Self-Perceived Efficacy of teachers'.
3. To know the interactive effect of Organizational Climate, the country and location (working in urban, semi-urban or rural educational institutions) on the Self-Perceived Efficacy of teachers' .)
4. To know the interactive effect of Organizational climate, the country of the origin and sex (male or female teachers) on the Self-Perceived Efficacy of teachers'.

Design of the Study

The present study used the Descriptive Survey method of research. Self-perceived Efficacy was considered as dependent variable whereas Organizational Climate was treated as independent variable. The present study is descriptive because it aims to describe the nature and present status of the phenomenon and it is concerned with conditions or relationships that exist

and opinions that are held. It involves some type of comparisons or contrasts between existing non-manipulated variables.

Sampling Technique

The sampling technique employed, in accordance with nature and objectives of the study will be random in nature.

Sample

The sample of the study shall consist of 1015 teachers from India and Bhutan. The teachers have been selected from rural and urban areas.

Inventory / Tools Used

The following inventory / tools were employed for the present study:

- Organizational Climate Inventory (OCI) developed by Chattopadhyay and Aggarwal (1976) for measuring Organizational Climate.
- Teacher Effectiveness Inventory developed by Parmod Kumar and Mutha (1982) for measuring Self Perceived Efficacy of Teachers.

Interpretations of Results

1.1 Analysis of relative contribution of Organizational Climate on Self-Perceived Efficacy of teachers for India, Bhutan and jointly for both the countries

Hypothesis: There is no relative contribution of Organizational Climate on Self-Perceived efficacy of teachers for India, Bhutan and jointly for both the countries.

The results of the same are depicted in table 1.1

Table 1.1

**Relative Importance of Organizational Climate on Self-perceived Efficacy of Teachers on
across the Countries**

COUNTRIES	A (P- VALUE)	B (P- VALUE)	ADJ R²	P-VALUE	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE
India	3.841 (000)	0.156 (000)	.028	13.781	.000
Bhutan	4.102 (000)	0.112 (000)	.023	14.725	.000
Both Countries	3.997 (000)	0.129 (000)	.024	26.011	.000

Table 1.1 depicts the relative importance of Organizational Climate on Self-Perceived Efficacy of teachers' on comparative basis for both the countries. India and Bhutan are similar and results revealed that Organizational Climate is having relative contribution upon Self Efficacy. As we compare both countries with each other, the position is not very different in both the countries as the value of 'b' beta coefficient is 0.156 (p-value=0.000) and 0.112 (p-value = 0.000) respectively for India and Bhutan. The value of 'b' beta for both the countries taken together is 0.129 (p-value=0.000).

3.1 Analysis of the effect of organizational climate, the country and other related attributes / variables on the self-perceived efficacy of teachers
Hypothesis: There is no interactive effect of overall Organizational climate including

Functional work climate & Dysfunctional work climate on the Self-Perceived Efficacy of teachers in India & Bhutan.

To test the above hypothesis ‘analysis of variance’ has been used where Self-perceived efficacy of teachers’ has been taken as dependent variable and Organizational Climate including Functional work climate & Dysfunctional work climate and country (India & Bhutan) has been taken as independent variable. The result of the same has been depicted in Table 3.1 and Table 3.2. Table 3.1 lists the descriptive statistics of self-perceived efficacy of teachers’ whereas Table 3.2 details the results of interaction analysis. (Tests of between-subjects effects)

Table 3.1 Descriptive Statistics

Org. Climate Category	Country of Respondent	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Dysfunctional Work Climate	Bhutan	4.412	0.331	133
	India	4.382	0.403	120
	Total	4.398	0.366	253
Functional Work Climate	Bhutan	4.487	0.267	442
	India	4.351	0.411	320
	Total	4.430	0.342	762
Total	Bhutan	4.469	0.285	575
	India	4.360	0.408	440
	Total	4.422	0.348	1015

It is evident that mean value has ranged from 4.351 to 4.487 with minimum for the functional work climate of India and maximum for the functional work climate of Bhutan. The value of standard deviation has ranged from 0.267 to 0.411. It is maximum for the functional work climate of India. The value is minimum for the functional work climate of Bhutan. This indicates that the teachers belonging to the functional work climate of Bhutan not only are high in perceiving their self-perceived efficacy but are consistent in their approach.

Table 3.2

Tests of between-subjects effects

Dependent Variable: Self-perceived Efficacy of Teachers'

Source	Type III Sum Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Model	19848.062 ^a	4	4962.015	42116.984	.000
Organizational Climate	.088	1	.088	0.743	0.389
Country	1.284	1	1.284	10.900	.001
Organizational Climate * Country	.527	1	.527	4.477	.035
Error	119.111	1011	.118		
Total	19967.173	1015			
^a R Squared = .994 (Adjusted R Squared = .994)					

From the result presented in Table 3.2 (tests of between-subjects effects) it is evident that there is no significant main effect of organizational climate (F-value = 0.743, p-value = 0.389) on the self-perceived efficacy of teachers. Dysfunctional work climate (mean=4.398) did not score significantly lower than functional work climate (Mean = 4.427). In addition there is significant main effect for Country (F-value=10.90), p-value = 0.001). Results show that Bhutan (Mean = 4.487) has scored higher than India (Mean = 4.351). The results also show that there is significant (p-value = 0.035) two-way (organizational culture by country) interaction. The scores between dysfunctional work climate and functional work climate and functional work climate did differ significantly among both the countries.

Hypothesis: There is no interactive effect of organizational climate, the country and location (working in urban, semi-urban or rural educational institutions) on the self-perceived efficacy of teachers’.

In order to test the above hypothesis analysis of variance has been used, where self-perceived efficacy of teachers’ has been taken as dependent variable. Organisational climate, the country and the location (working in urban, semi-urban or rural educational institution) has been taken as independent variable. The results of the same have been depicted in Table 3.3 and Table 3.4. Descriptive statistics of self-perceived efficacy of teachers’ have been listed in Table 3.3 where as Table 3.4 details the result of interaction analysis.

Table 3.3 Descriptive Statistics

Org. Climate Category	Country of Respondent	Location	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Dysfunctional Work Climate	Bhutan	Urban	4.474	0.337	47

Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ)

(Bi-Monthly) Peer-Reviewed Journal Vol No III Issues V
ISSN 2278-5655

		Rural	4.370	0.306	10
		Semi-urban	4.379	0.329	76
		Total	4.412	0.331	133
	India	Urban	4.384	0.406	63
		Rural	4.368	0.398	21
		Semi-urban	4.308	0.410	26
		Total	4.363	0.403	110
	Total	Urban	4.423	0.379	110
		Rural	4.369	0.366	31
		Semi-urban	4.361	0.351	102
		Total	4.390	0.366	243
Functinal Climate	Bhutan	Urban	4.493	0.250	155
		Rural	4.440	0.285	38
		Semi-urban	4.490	0.275	249
		Total	4.487	0.267	442
	India	Urban	4.335	0.410	218
		Rural	4.410	0.281	47

		Semi-urban	4.438	0.371	31
		Total	4.357	0.389	296
	Total	Urban	4.401	0.361	373
		Rural	4.423	0.282	85
		Semi-urban	4.484	0.287	280
		Total	4.435	0.328	738

It is evident from Table 3.3 that the mean value ranged from 4.361 to 4.493 with maximum for the urban teachers of Bhutan under the category of functional work climate and minimum for semi-urban teachers of India under the category of dysfunctional work climate. The values of standard deviation ranged from 0.250 to 0.409 with the minimum for the urban teachers of Bhutan under the category of functional work climate indicating consistency in the response of the subjects of this group. Standard deviation has been maximum for the urban teachers of India under the category of overall work climate indicating that the subjects of this group have relatively more divergent views. The number of subjects in each category has also been listed in the last column of the Table. 3.4. As stated earlier Table 3.4 lists the results of the tests between subject effects (two-way and three-way interaction). Among the main effects it is evident that for organizational climate there was a statistically insignificant at 5 per cent effect (F -value= 2.806 and P -value 0.094). For the country there has also been significant effect (F = 4.441 and P -value 0.035).

Table 3.4 Tests of between-subjects effects

Dependent variable: Self-perceived Efficacy of Teachers'

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	Sig.
Model	19200.553 ^a	12	1600.046	14419.225	.000
Organisational Climate	.311	1	.311	2.806	.094
Country	.493	1	.493	4.441	.035
Location	.063	2	.031	.282	.754
Organisational Climate * Country	.017	1	.017	.158	.691
Organisational Climate * Location	.552	2	.276	2.489	.084
Country * Location	.245	2	.122	1.103	.332
Organisational Climate * Country * Location	.057	2	.029	.257	.773
Error	107.526	969	.111		
Total	19308.079	981			

The position of the location (working in urban, semi-urban or rural educational institution) also exhibits insignificant effect ($F=0.282$ and $P\text{-value} = 0.754$). As regards the two-way interaction effects, if organizational climate and the country are taken together the effect is

also insignificant (F-value= 0.158 and P-value 0.691). The position for organizational climate and the location (working in urban, semi-urban or rural educational institution) taken together also show the joint effect to be insignificant at 5 per cent (F-value = 2.489 and P-value = 0.084). Lastly, the position of the country and the location (working in urban, semi-urban or rural educational institution) taken together indicate that effect to be insignificant (F-value=1.103 and P-value = 0.332).As regards the position of three-way interaction when all the three independent variables taken together, i.e., organizational climate, the country and the location (working in urban, semi-urban or rural educational institution) also show the results to be insignificant (F-value = 0.257 and P-value = 0.773).Thus, on the whole it is concluded that except for country all the other results are insignificant.

Hypothesis: There is no interactive effect of organizational climate, the country of the origin and sex (male or female teachers) on the self-perceived efficacy of teachers’.

In order to test the above hypothesis analysis of variance has been used, where self-perceived efficacy of teachers’ has been taken as dependent variable. Organisational climate, the country and the sex (male or female working teachers) has been taken as independent variable. The results of the same have been depicted in Table 3.5 and Table 3.6. Descriptive statistics of self-perceived efficacy of teachers’ have been listed in Table 3.5 where as Table 3.6 details the result of interaction analysis.

Table 3.5 Descriptive Statistics

Org. Climate Category	Country of Respondent	Gender of Respondent	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Dysfunctional Work	Bhutan	Male	4.378	0.356	86
		Female	4.474	0.272	47

Climate	India	Total	4.412	0.331	133	
		Male	4.333	0.312	25	
		Female	4.395	0.424	95	
	Total	Total	4.382	0.403	120	
		Male	4.368	0.346	111	
		Female	4.421	0.381	142	
	Funcional Work Climate	Bhutan	Total	4.398	0.366	253
			Male	4.492	0.268	251
			Female	4.479	0.268	191
India		Total	4.487	0.267	442	
		Male	4.341	0.421	67	
		Female	4.354	0.409	253	
Total		Total	4.351	0.411	320	
		Male	4.460	0.312	318	
		Female	4.408	0.360	444	
Total	Bhutan	Total	4.430	0.342	762	
		Male	4.463	0.296	337	
		Female	4.478	0.268	238	

	Total	4.469	0.285	575
India	Male	4.339	0.393	92
	Female	4.365	0.413	348
	Total	4.360	0.408	440
Total	Male	4.436	0.323	429
	Female	4.411	0.365	586
	Total	4.422	0.348	1015

It is evident from Table 3.5 that the mean value ranged from 4.492 to 4.333 with maximum for the male teachers of Bhutan under the category of functional work climate and minimum for male teachers of India under the category of dysfunctional work climate. The values of standard deviation ranged from 0.267 to 0.424 with minimum for the of the teachers of Bhutan under the category of functional work climate indicating consistency in the response of the subjects under this category. Standard deviation has been maximum for the female teachers of India under the category of dysfunctional work climate indicating that the subjects of this group have relatively more divergent views. The number of subjects in each category has also been listed in the last column of the Table. 3.5.

Table 3.6 Tests of between-subjects effects

Dependent variable: Self-perceived Efficacy of Teachers'

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Model	19848.441 ^a	8	2481.055	21042.463	.000

Organisational Climate	.067	1	.067	.564	.453
Country	1.437	1	1.437	12.187	.001
Sex	.223	1	.223	1.893	.169
Organisational Climate * Country	.209	1	.209	1.770	.184
Organisational Climate * sex	.225	1	.225	1.905	.168
Country * sex	.000	1	.000	.004	.948
Organisational Climate * Country * sex	.029	1	.029	.249	.618
Error	118.732	1007	.118		
Total	19967.173	1015			
a. R Squared = .994 (Adjusted R Squared = .994)					

As stated earlier Table 3.6 lists the results of the tests between subject effects (main effect, two-way) and three-way interaction). Among the main effects it is evident that for organizational climate there was a statistically insignificant effect (F-value= 0.564 and P-value 0.453). For the country there has also been significant effect (F= 12.187 and P-value 0.001). The position of the sex (male or female working teachers) also exhibits insignificant effect (F=1.893 and P-value = 0.169). As regards the two-way interaction effects, if organisation climate and the country are taken together the effect is also insignificant (F-value= 1.770 and P-value 0.184).

The position for organizational climate and the sex (male or female working teachers) taken together show the joint effect to be insignificant (F-value = 1.905 and P-value = 0.168). Lastly, the position of the country and the sex (male or female working teachers) taken together indicate that effect to be insignificant (F-value=0.004 and P-value = 0.948).As regards the position of three-way interaction when all the three independent variables taken together, i.e., organizational climate, the country and the sex (male or female working teachers) also show the results to be insignificant (F-value = 0.249 and P-value = 0.618).Thus, on the whole it is concluded that except for country all the other results are insignificant.

Results and Discussion:

1. India and Bhutan are having similar positions and findings revealed that Organizational Climate is having relative contribution on Self Efficacy. As we compare both countries with each other in terms of Organizational Climate and Self Perceived Efficacy, the position is not very different in both the countries.
2. It is evident that mean value is minimum for the functional work climate of India and maximum for the functional work climate of Bhutan.
3. Teachers belonging to the functional work climate of Bhutan not only are high in perceiving their self-perceived efficacy but are consistent in their approach.
4. Dysfunctional work climate did not score significantly lower than functional work climate. The scores between dysfunctional work climate and functional work climate did differ significantly among both the countries. .
5. It is evident from that mean value is maximum for the urban teachers of Bhutan under the category of functional work climate and minimum for semi-urban teachers of India under the category of dysfunctional work climate. Standard deviation has been maximum for the urban teachers of India under the category of overall work climate indicating that the subjects of this group have relatively more divergent views. Findings revealed that urban

teachers of Bhutan under the category of functional work climate indicating consistency in the response of the subjects of this group.

6. The position of the sex (male or female working teachers) also exhibits insignificant effect. It is evident that mean value is maximum for the male teachers of Bhutan under the category of functional work climate and minimum for male teachers of India under the category of dysfunctional work climate.

Educational Implications: The findings of the present study have important implications for improving both countries in terms of the organizational climate and self efficacy. Policy makers should understand and promote teacher efficacy beliefs. Results of present research revealed that Bhutan and India are having similar conditions in terms of organizational climate and self efficacy; they should try to do collaborative efforts for making organizational climate and self efficacy for strengthened.

References:

- Bandura, A. (1997) *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*, New York: Freeman& Company
- Jaafari, P, Karami & Soleimani, N. (2012). The Relationship among Organizational Climate, Organizational Learning and Teachers' Self Efficacy. *Procedia-Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 47(01), pp.2212-2218.
- Marsh, H. W., & Hau, K. T. (2004). Explaining Paradoxical Relations between Academic Self-Concepts and Achievements: Cross-Cultural Generalizability of the Internal/External Frame of Reference Predictions across 26 Countries. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 96(1), pp.56-67.
- Pritchard, R. D., & Karasick, B. W. (1973). The effects of organizational climate on managerial job performance and job satisfaction. *Organizational behavior and human performance*, 9(1), pp.126-146.
- Reichers, A. E., and Schneider, B. (1990). Climate and culture: an evolution of constructs. In B. Schneider (Ed.), *Organizational climate and culture*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.

- Schwarzer, R., & Hallum, S. (2008). Perceived teacher self-efficacy as a predictor of job stress and burnout: Mediation analyses. *Applied Psychology: An International Review*, 57, pp.152-171. (Special Issue:Health and Well-Being).
- Schwarzer, R., & Jerusalem, M. (1995). Generalized self-efficacy scale. *Measures in health psychology: A user's portfolio. Causal and control beliefs*, 1, pp.35-37.
- Shacklock, A., Manning, M., & Hort, L. (2013). Self-efficacy as an intervening variable between ethical work climate and decision making. *e-Journal of Social & Behavioural Research in Business*, 4(2), pp.1-13.
- Stajkovic, A., & Luthans, F. (1998). Self-efficacy And Work-related Performance: A Meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 124(02), pp.240-261.
- Triandis, H. (1996). The Psychological Measurement of Cultural Syndromes. *American Psychologist*, 51, pp.407-415.
- Voiceofindia.com 2013
- Woolfolk, A. E., & Hoy, W. K. (1990). Prospective teachers' sense of efficacy and beliefs about control. *Journal of educational Psychology*, 82(1), 81.
- Yahyagil, M. (2006). The fit between the concepts of organizational culture and climate. *Journal of Organizational Culture, Communications and Conflict*, 10(2), pp.77–104.

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